

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS AND MECHANISMS OF ATTRACTING FOREIGN INVESTMENT

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Analysis of socio-economic changes taking place in our country shows that the modernization of the economy, and for this purpose the active investment policy, plays a very important role in the achievements and successes achieved. Accordingly, it is important to create an effective system for managing the socio-economic development of the regions of the republic, to study the theoretical and methodological foundations for assessing the attractiveness and potential of their investment environment. No matter which developed country we consider, we will witness the progressive results of the trends related to the country's economy, first of all, as a result of the soundness of the investment environment, its attractiveness, and the rapid inflow of investment flows.

According to foreign scientist Yurii A.Rolik, investment attractiveness is a set of characteristics that allow a potential investor to assess how attractive a particular investment object is compared to others for the purpose of investing available funds [1]. According to economists E.Sojli and W.Thamlar, the more favorable the investment environment, the lower the investor's entrepreneurial risk, and this activates the influx of investors. On the contrary, if the investment environment is unfavorable, the risk level is high. This leads to an increase in the costs of the investment recipient. In addition, it was noted that the state of the investment environment is important not only for the investor, but also for the recipient of the investment [2]

Scientist G. Svitlana in her research proved that increasing investment attractiveness is a factor contributing to the effective functioning, development and growth of a company in modern competitive conditions, while in economically developed countries the investment process depends on the influence of market conditions, sources of financing and the volume of investments [3].

According to local economist S. Elmirzayev, companies in the country should determine the normative ratio between dividends and reinvestment in their dividend policy, protect the rights of minority shareholders, achieve an increase in share prices on the market, expand business activities, etc. which, in turn, has a positive effect on the investment attractiveness of the country [4].

The research of the well-known scientist, economist N. Jumayev, indicates the need to pay attention to the following in order to ensure investment attractiveness and rational use of investment potential:

- the region's potential, aimed at increasing investment attractiveness in order to stabilize the economy;
- accelerating investment activities aimed at innovative renewal of the socio-economic structure;
- increasing the level of diversification and innovative investments, which will provide the first appearance of regional research [5].

In his scientific treatises, the local economist A. Shomirov emphasized that in attracting foreign investments, regardless of the field in which joint-stock companies operate, it is important to allocate additional financial resources, including the priority goal of attracting foreign investments, and in this regard, one of the most modern methods of attracting investments in joint-stock companies is the IPO mechanism [6].

Investment attractiveness is determined by the simultaneous influence of the country's investment potential and the level of investment risk. Such indicators help determine the feasibility and attractiveness of investments. The level of investment risk is directly related to the investment environment.

The investment environment is reflected at the macroeconomic level, that is, in the relations between the investor and specific state bodies and economic entities. The investment environment is an objective state for any specific time and includes a set of conditions for investing capital. However, the investment environment is formed under the influence of the management activities of state bodies. Therefore, the state's investment policy is one of the most important factors. In this sense, each state has its own specific capital acceptance system when importing capital. The worse the level of the investment environment, the higher the investor sets his risk.

Attracting and fully utilizing foreign direct investment contributes to increasing employment and living standards in the country, improving the income of the population, and increasing the investment attractiveness of our country in the international arena.

Based on the above scientific proposals and recommendations, their in-depth study, analysis and substantiated implementation in practice will yield results in the near future. In addition, creating a favorable investment climate in the country will have a positive impact on further increasing the state's investment attractiveness.

List of used literature:

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